

**ПОЭТИКА РУМЫНСКОЙ НАРОДНОЙ БАЛЛАДЫ
«МАСТЕР МАНОЛЕ» В ПЕРЕВОДЕ ДАВИДА САМОЙЛОВА /
THE POETICS OF THE ROMANIAN FOLK BALLAD
“MASTER MANOLE” IN DAVID SAMOYLOV’S TRANSLATION**

Aliona BREABINA, PhD Student

(“Alecu Russo” Balti State University, Republic of Moldova)

breabinaalena@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2618-5062>

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This work will focus on preserving the poetics of the Romanian folk ballad “Master Manole”, a pearl of folk art, translated by David Samoilov. The Russian poet most accurately and subtly conveyed the artistic originality of the legend, which became a source of inspiration for him. The legend was first published by the Romanian writer Vasile Alexandri under the title “Manastirea Argesului” (Monastery of Arges) in the book “Balade adunate si indreptate” (*Collected and Reworked Ballads*), Iasi, 1852. Next, Lucian Blaga showed a new interpretation of the legend, in which Manole was not punished by Negru Voda, but rather jumped off the roof. Gheorghe Voda published a collection of poems “Wings for Manole” and others. Literary ballads are a clear example of how the dialogue of cultures is developing in world literature, as well as the huge role of translations, creating a common cultural base. Translations are an important impetus for original creativity. David Samoilov (David Samuilovich Kaufman) stepped far beyond the front-line poets and constantly strived

for perfection. Time and the culture of other peoples, included in his work, significantly transformed his poetic style. New horizons opened for Samoilov, where stylization became a characteristic feature, reflecting his deep appreciation for folk art - an art form that conveys the thoughts, feelings, and experiences of the people. Folk art is defined by heightened emotionality, airiness, and musical harmony. Highly appreciating Samoilov's translations, P. Antokolsky wrote: "Samoilov has a rich vocabulary, he has an excellent command of his native language and poetry, he has sophisticated rhythmic technique and enviable intonation freedom in translating someone else's colloquial speech". The Romanian ballad, translated by Samoilov, acquired an independent life in its native poetic and linguistic element. He used the techniques of transformation, metamorphosis, Romanian rhythm, motives, images, which allowed him to create a picture of life as constant movement and the transformation of artistic forms into each other. He used comparison techniques - "Anna-beauty", "flower of the field"; metaphors - "dressing a wife, dressing her in stone", "she was bent by the wind", "the building grew up", "the wall is shaking me, squeezing my ribs, breaking my child!"; epithets - "for good memory", "Beauty Anna", "the first craftsman", "lesser craftsmen", "great architects", in which he drew the reader's attention to important details, ancient myths of the Romanesque peoples, telling about the founding of cities, castles, towers, etc. Samoilov succeeded in characteristic mythological thinking and the motive of merging the natural world with the human. In this ballad, Samoilov embodied in detail the mechanism of "creative" death, which has passed down from ancient beliefs to our time, as well as the image of a hero who freely and confidently feels himself an organic part of the world.